

Constraints on Lorentz and CPT violation from muon-electron conversion

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Abstract

Charged lepton flavor violation (CLFV) is a popular target in searches for new physics. We demonstrate how the search for violations of an accidental symmetry of the Standard Model can also be connected to the search for violations of more fundamental symmetries. Working in the Standard-Model Extension (SME), a Lorentz- and CPT-violating effective field theory, we investigate the conversion of a muon to an electron in an atomic environment. A subset of the contributing operators are uniquely constrained by this channel, and their bounds (coming from the SINDRUM II experiment) are the first such reported. We further provide sensitivity estimates for the upcoming searches by the Mu2e and COMET experiments. We also discuss the experimental signature which would indicate Lorentz violation and a method which could provide greater sensitivity in future analyses and help to distinguish between the contributions of different operators.

1 Introduction

In the Standard Model (SM), neutrinos are considered to be massless, leading to an accidental global symmetry that conserves lepton flavor. The observation of mass-driven neutrino oscillations demonstrates that this is not an exact symmetry in nature, but extending the SM only to include neutrino masses still predicts that CLFV should be suppressed far beyond current experimental limits. Due to the smallness of the neutrino masses and the GIM mechanism, such processes are expected to have branching ratios on the order of 10^{-54} or less [1–3]; thus, any experimental observation of CLFV would be interpreted as a clear signal of new physics.

One popular channel for CLFV searches is the coherent conversion of a muon to an electron in the presence of a nucleus, $\mu^- + \frac{A}{Z}N \rightarrow e^- + \frac{A}{Z}N$; here, “coherent” means that the state of the nucleus remains unchanged by the interaction. In these experiments, a muon beam is collided with an atomic target to create short-lived muonic atoms. Many muons will be captured by the nucleus through the exchange of a W boson, $\mu^- + \frac{A}{Z}N \rightarrow \nu_\mu + \frac{A}{Z-1}N$, while others will decay in orbit, $\mu^- \rightarrow e^- \bar{\nu}_e \nu_\mu$, yielding an electron with the energy spectrum characteristic to a three-body decay. If the CLFV process $\mu^- + \frac{A}{Z}N \rightarrow e^- + \frac{A}{Z}N$ occurs, however, the electron will be monoenergetic with energy $E_e^{\text{conv}} = m_\mu - E_{\text{bind}} - E_{\text{recoil}}$, where m_μ is the muon mass, E_{bind} is the binding energy of the muonic atom in the 1S state, and E_{recoil} is the (negligible) nuclear recoil energy. The goal is to observe this signal as an excess over the expected three-body spectrum; although experiments have so far failed to do so, they are still able to set upper bounds on the ratio of the rate of the CLFV process to the capture rate:

$$R_{\mu e} \equiv \frac{\omega_{\text{conv}}}{\omega_{\text{capt}}} = \frac{\Gamma(\mu^- + \frac{A}{Z}N \rightarrow e^- + \frac{A}{Z}N)}{\Gamma(\mu^- + \frac{A}{Z}N \rightarrow \nu_\mu + \frac{A}{Z-1}N)}. \quad (1)$$

The best limit on this ratio was set by the SINDRUM II experiment at the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI): $R_{\mu e} < 7 \times 10^{-13}$ at 90% confidence level (CL) on a gold ($^{197}_{79}\text{Au}$) target [4]. The

next generation of experiments consists of COMET at the Japan Proton Accelerator Complex (J-PARC) and Mu2e at the Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory (Fermilab), both on aluminum ($^{27}_{13}\text{Al}$) targets. COMET will have a Phase I sensitivity of $R_{\mu e} \simeq 7 \times 10^{-15}$ and a final sensitivity of $R_{\mu e} \simeq 2.6 \times 10^{-17}$, both at 90% CL [5]. Mu2e will have a Run I sensitivity of $R_{\mu e} \simeq 6.2 \times 10^{-16}$ and a final sensitivity of $R_{\mu e} \simeq 8 \times 10^{-17}$, both at 90% CL [6, 7].

2 CLFV from Lorentz- and CPT-violating operators

Lorentz invariance and CPT are exact symmetries of the SM, but small violations of these symmetries may arise from unified theories of gravity and quantum physics [8–10]. In order to study the new operators which are permitted once these symmetries are relaxed, an effective field theory known as the Standard-Model Extension (SME) [11–15] is used. In the SME, the leading contributions to nuclear $\mu-e$ conversion are from mass-dimension five electromagnetic operators (involving the electric field of the nucleus) and mass-dimension six four-point quark-lepton operators. At tree level, the quark-lepton operators are uniquely accessed in this experimental channel, while the electromagnetic operators can also be constrained by other searches, such as $\mu \rightarrow e\gamma$.

The muon is bound to the nucleus in the 1S ground state, and the free (plane-wave) electron still experiences the effects of the nuclear electric field. To account for this, one needs to obtain the leptonic wavefunctions, which can be written

$$\psi_{\kappa,s}(r, \theta, \phi) = (g(r)\chi_{\kappa,s}(\theta, \phi), if(r)\chi_{-\kappa,s}(\theta, \phi))^T \quad (2)$$

The eigenspinors satisfy $(\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{l} + I)\chi_{\kappa,s} = -\kappa\chi_{\kappa,s}$ and $J_z\chi_{\kappa,s} = s\chi_{\kappa,s}$ for $\kappa = \mp(J + 1/2)$. The radial wavefunctions can be found by numerically solving the Dirac equation, utilizing the spherically-symmetric nuclear charge distributions which have been tabulated in the literature [16, 17].

For the electromagnetic operators, the coherent conversion rate is given by

$$\omega_{conv}^{(5)} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=\pm\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{\kappa=\pm 1} \sum_{s'=\pm\frac{1}{2}} \left| \int d^3x \bar{\psi}_{\kappa,s'}^{(e)\dagger} \mathcal{O}^{\alpha\beta} \psi_s^{(\mu)} F_{\alpha\beta} \right|^2, \quad (3)$$

where $F_{\alpha\beta}$ is the electromagnetic field strength tensor containing the electric field of the nucleus, $\bar{\psi}_{\kappa,s'}^{(e)\dagger}$ is the continuum wavefunction of an electron of energy E_e^{conv} and spin s' , and $\psi_s^{(\mu)}$ is the 1S bound-state wavefunction of a muon of spin s . The angular integration is over the region of geometric acceptance of the particular experiment being studied; for those considered here, we assume full 2π coverage in the azimuthal angle and coverage over a region symmetric about $\theta = \pi/2$ with respect to the beamline for the polar angle. The SME operators are denoted by $\mathcal{O}^{\alpha\beta} \in \left\{ (m_F^{(5)})_{\mu e}^{\alpha\beta}, i(m_{5F}^{(5)})_{\mu e}^{\alpha\beta} \gamma^5, (a_F^{(5)})_{\mu e}^{\mu\alpha\beta} \gamma_\mu, (b_F^{(5)})_{\mu e}^{\mu\alpha\beta} \gamma^5 \gamma_\mu, \frac{1}{2} (H_F^{(5)})_{\mu e}^{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} \sigma_{\mu\nu} \right\}$, with the restriction that one of the indices $\{\alpha, \beta\}$ is temporal and the other spatial (as only the nuclear electric field is considered). All operators are Lorentz-violating; those whose coefficients have an odd number of Lorentz indices are also CPT-violating.

The coherent conversion rate for the quark-lepton operators is given by

$$\omega_{conv}^{(6)} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=\pm\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{\kappa=\pm 1} \sum_{s'=\pm\frac{1}{2}} \left| \int d^3x \left(\alpha \bar{\psi}_{\kappa,s'}^{(e)\dagger} \mathcal{K} \psi_s^{(\mu)} + \beta \bar{\psi}_{\kappa,s'}^{(e)\dagger} \mathcal{K}_0 \psi_s^{(\mu)} \right) \right|^2, \quad (4)$$

where the nuclear matrix elements which are nonvanishing for coherent conversion [17] are denoted by $\alpha = \sum_q \langle N | \bar{\psi}^{(q)} \psi^{(q)} | N \rangle$ for $q \in \{u, d, s\}$ and $\beta = \sum_q \langle N | \bar{\psi}^{(q)} \gamma_0 \psi^{(q)} | N \rangle$ for $q \in \{u, d\}$. The SME operators are denoted by $\mathcal{K} \in \left\{ (k_{SV}^{(6)})_{qq\mu e}^\lambda \gamma_\lambda, (k_{SA}^{(6)})_{qq\mu e}^\lambda \gamma^5 \gamma_\lambda, \frac{1}{2} (k_{ST}^{(6)})_{qq\mu e}^{\kappa\lambda} \sigma_{\kappa\lambda} \right\}$

Table 1: Constraints based on SINDRUM II results.

Operator Class	Constraint
Electromagnetic	$< 8 \times 10^{-12} \text{ GeV}^{-1}$
Scalar Quark-Lepton (u, d)	$< 7 \times 10^{-13} \text{ GeV}^{-2}$
Scalar Quark-Lepton (s)	$< 15 \times 10^{-13} \text{ GeV}^{-2}$
γ_0 Quark-Lepton (u, d)	$< 30 \times 10^{-13} \text{ GeV}^{-2}$

and $\mathcal{K}_0 \in \left\{ (k_{VS}^{(6)})^t_{qq\mu e}, i(k_{VP}^{(6)})^t_{qq\mu e} \gamma^5, \frac{1}{2}(k_{VV}^{(6)})^{t\lambda}_{qq\mu e} \gamma_\lambda, (k_{VA}^{(6)})^{t\lambda}_{qq\mu e} \gamma^5 \gamma_\lambda, \frac{1}{2}(k_{VT}^{(6)})^{t\kappa\lambda}_{qq\mu e} \sigma_{\kappa\lambda} \right\}$. As above, all operators are Lorentz-violating, and those whose coefficients have an odd number of Lorentz indices are also CPT-violating.

Since the SME coefficients listed above carry Lorentz indices, if they are nonzero they can violate Lorentz invariance and thus spacetime isotropy; this means that one has to take into account time and location in order to compare results across experiments. This is accomplished by quoting results in a standard reference frame, conventionally chosen to be the Sun-Centered Frame (SCF). The SCF is defined as having $T = 0$ at the 2000 vernal equinox, the X axis directed from the Earth to the Sun at that time, and the Z axis parallel to the rotation axis of the Earth [18, 19]. The leading contribution to the coordinate transformation to a standard laboratory frame (x axis towards local south, y axis towards local east) on Earth is given as Eq. (7) of Ref. [20]. It depends on the colatitude of the laboratory, the sidereal frequency of the Earth, and the sidereal time (shifted from T by an amount that depends on longitude, among other effects [21, 22]). We use the beamline to define the polar z axis, relating it to the z axis in the standard lab frame by an additional improper rotation.

The result of the coordinate transformation is that the conversion rate in the SCF contains both time-independent contributions and harmonics in the sidereal frequency of the earth. While we time-average our results to reflect the extended collection period of the experiments, one should keep in mind that time-stamped experimental data would provide additional sensitivity to specific operators and that a CLFV signal oscillating in sidereal time would strongly suggest a Lorentz-violating origin.

3 Results and Outlook

Using the results of the SINDRUM II experiment, we are able to constrain the relevant coefficients of both the electromagnetic and the quark-lepton SME operators. A summary of these results is provided in Table 1; detailed results, along with projections for the initial phases of COMET and Mu2e, are available in Ref. [23].

The constraints on the electromagnetic operators are weaker, by about an order of magnitude, than those previously obtained [20] from the MEG experiment at PSI, which probed $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ \gamma$ [24]. The MEG II experiment is currently taking data [25] and will further improve those bounds, although the later-stage results of COMET and Mu2e may be even more restrictive. The quark-lepton operators, for which our constraints are the first such reported [26], are experimentally accessible at tree level only in this channel, which thus remains complementary to the other $\mu - e$ conversion searches.

The expected sensitivities of the upcoming COMET and Mu2e experiments suggest at least an order of magnitude improvement in the limits after their initial phases; reaching their final sensitivity goals could lead to improvement by two orders of magnitude over the current constraints.

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